

D2.2 LEA PPI/PCP funding report

**Guidelines and recommendations to attract funding for
upcoming PPI/PCP calls**

31 October 2018

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Project acronym: LEA

Project title: Learning Technology Accelerator

Grant Agreement number: 779803

Coordinator: Jyväskylän Yliopisto

Project funded by the European Commission, H2020

Funding Scheme: H2020-ICT-2017-1

Due date of deliverable:	M8, October 2018
Actual submission date:	M8, 31 st of October 2018
Start date of the project:	March 1, 2018
Project duration:	24 months

Workpackage	2
Task(s)	T2.2 Preparations of PPI/PCP
Lead beneficiary	EU Projektkonsult AB (EUPK)
Editor/ authors	Ellinor Wallin, Gabrielle Eriksson
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Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. Introduction

This report aims to provide information to public procuring organisations interested in participating in the upcoming LEA PPI and PCP projects on the relevant and available upcoming European H2020 programme calls, to give information about available funding opportunities on both EU and national level, and to give an overview of the necessary and basic essentials of planning and conducting the PPI/PCP projects.

1.1 Timeline

This report focuses to align LEA preparations with two mayor H2020 calls.

- PPI call COSME, submission deadline December 2018.
- PCP call ICT 34, submission deadline March 2019.

2. PPI funding strategy

This section contains:

- The call description.
- The overall strategy combining several levels of financial support to engage the LEA partners.
- Detailed information on the EU specific PPI call.
- Basic information and important guidelines on national funding in several member states.

2.1 Objectives and expected outcomes of the call

Extract from the COSME program

The specific objective of this call in relation to SMEs is to improve their access to markets inside the European Union. Access to public procurement remains **difficult for SMEs, who are only awarded 45% of the value of public contracts above EU public procurement threshold**. This share is clearly below their weight in the economy.

The public sector can play a large role in helping companies, and in particular SMEs, overcome a classic market failure: finding a first group of customers for their innovative products and services. **Innovation is constrained by a 'chicken or egg problem,' whereby suppliers will often wait until there is a demonstrated demand before they develop new solutions, while at the same time the potential buyers are waiting to see a new product or service enjoying some success in the market before they will risk buying it themselves (Cate et al, 1998).**

This call for proposals is expected to contribute to a significant increase in the proportion of SMEs that have access to the public procurement market. It will also increase the visibility and awareness of the advantages of procuring innovation for a constantly increasing greater number of public buyers.

This call for proposals has three main objectives:

1. The first objective is to **encourage cooperation between public buyers to promote the use of public procurement to contribute to the development of innovation.**

2. The second objective is to **use public procurement as a mechanism to pilot innovation** in areas of strong public interest such as, for instance, clean energy (contributing to the Paris targets for fighting climate change) or healthcare. This will in turn encouraging innovative EU companies, in particular SMEs, to develop new solutions to address societal challenges.
3. The third objective is **to link and establish synergies with research and innovation projects funded by the EU (via Horizon 2020, COSME or EU funding programmes) whenever possible.**

PPI definition according to COSME call

Public Procurement represents approximately 14% of the EU GDP. However, less than half of this budget is purchased from SMEs.

Public procurement of innovation (PPI) broadly refers to any public procurement that has one or both of the following aspects:

- buying the process of innovation;
- buying the outcomes of innovation.

Public procurement of innovation may commence with research and development of products, services or processes that do not yet exist. Public buyers state their need, with little to no concrete idea of the solution, and support innovative businesses and researchers in finding the perfectly suited product, service or process. In this way, the **public buyer effectively becomes part of the innovation lifecycle from the very beginning** of product or service development.

Furthermore, **public buyers may choose innovative products, services or processes that are new in the market instead of renewing or replicating existing procurement contracts.**

The PPI methodology to be applied in LEA

In order to meet this call and align LEA with a possible COSME call beneficial for LEA procurers this sections presents the methodology we apply in LEA.

A PPI shall follow two steps 1) Preparatory stage and 2) Executive stage (including deployment). LEA will prepare the PPI **but not launch** the PPI call (the launching of the call will be done separately in for example the COSME project).

LEA uses the following methodology:

1. Identify and agree on the common needs for the PPI (WP 3).
2. Update the market analysis for 2018 and beyond of innovative solutions on the market (WP 4).
3. Perform an Open market consultation (WP 6).
4. Prepare the ITT documentation (WP 5).
5. General preparation of the PPI and create a strategy for funding of the PPI on both EU and national level as well as to open up LEA School Labs for deployment of the solutions (WP 2).

Additionally, the procurers need to define the legal framework of the upcoming PPI adopted to provide them most benefits. Underneath is a description of a joint PPI procurement.

Joint PPI procurement is when two or more procurers, with the same needs for either a technology and/or methodology, team up to carry out all the preparations, knowledge exchange and market consultation to publish one common call for tender (if needed with multiple lots). The execution of the procurement procedure is conducted jointly and lead by the lead procurer, appointed by the buyers group, who publishes the call for tender in the name and on behalf of the whole buyers group, under the applicable legal framework for public procurement in the country of the lead procurer. The evaluations of the service offers are made jointly, based on common specifications and criteria defined by the buyers group.

Each procurer in the buyers group can, based on the framework agreement established by the lead procurer with several suppliers under the lead procurers' national law, individually award and sign specific contracts under their own national procurement legislation (with or without reopening of competition under the pre-established framework agreement) at the same time or at different times during the project.

Note: Some national legislations may not allow procurers to be authorized to delegate competences to another (lead) procurer or to assume responsibilities as lead procurer for other (countries) procurers. This must be checked and cleared before entering the joint procurement agreement.

The recommendation from the LEA Innovation procurement expert team (Ms. Sara Bedin, Ms. Ellinor Wallin and Ms. Gabrielle Eriksson) is to explore the **Occasional Joint Cross-border PPI Procurement** approach for the LEA PPI.

2.2 Detailed information on COSME call

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/cosme/topics/cos-ppi-2018-2-01.html>

Specific timeline COSME PPI call:

Stages	Dates
a) Deadline for submitting applications	11/12/2018 17:00 h Brussels time
b) Evaluation period*	12/2018
c) Information to applicants*	04/2019
d) Signature of grant agreements*	07/2019
e) Starting date of the action*	08/2019

PPI COSME funding conditions in brief

- Joint PPI (see details in LEA D2.1)
- Between 2-7 procurers, adding experts on learning technology, legal and PPI experts as support organisations (max 10 partners).
- Proposal submission in December 2018 and project start in May 2019.
- Project time: 2.5 years.
- Proposal length: 25 pages.
- Budget: 2-3 projects approved total 4 million € (up to 1.5 million €).
- 90 % EU funding of eligible costs.
- 25% EU funding of eligible costs to purchase the innovative products.
- Maximum 60% of the EU funding can be allocated to and spent on the purchase(s) of the innovative solution(s).

Expected budget PPI project

The grant is limited to:

- A maximum reimbursement rate of 90% of eligible costs (direct personal cost, subcontracting, other direct costs, eligible indirect costs (7%), linked to the collaboration, procurement preparation and follow-up of the public tender; and
- A maximum reimbursement rate of 25% of the eligible costs (the actual purchase of the innovative solution(s)).

The estimated EU contribution allocated to the purchase of the innovative solution(s) may not exceed 60% of the maximum EU contribution requested.

Note: EC only covers 25% of the purchase of innovative solutions and 75% of investments/funding is required to be covered by the procurers.

2.3 PPI call funding and levels

In order to provide funding (risk investments) for the upcoming PPI call based upon shared EU funding and public investment several levels of funding and programs can be combined:

Division of costs between EU and national level funds

The COSME H2020 call provides EU funding of:

- Preparations (finetune of award criteria, ITT documentation, market engagement).
- Publication of the PPI call.
- Evaluation of the tenders.
- Evaluation of the PPI project as a whole and the lessons learned.
- Capacity building and transfer of knowledge to the Learntech community.
- Actual purchase(s) as first customers can be funded with 25%.

National programs in procurers member states eg. ERDF or national innovation programs provides funding of:

- Additional funding (up to 75%) on acutal PPI solutions purchase(s).
- National dissemination and sharing of lessons learned.

Calculated budget possible scenario 1.5 million € in total and 6 procurers

Budget	Notes
800 000 € CSA budget	PM, travel, subcontracting etc. to publish the call, conduct tests, evaluation, dissemination.
700 000 € purchase	46.5 % of total EU contribution
2 800 000 € purchase total	25% EU funding
2 100 000 € procurers investment	from national programs 350 000 € per partner

2.4 Possible PPI project rationale

In order to speed up the process of preparing an upcoming proposal this section includes a project scope in brief aligned with expected preparations of the PPI in LEA and for the upcoming COSME call.

Some parts will be covered by LEA actions and shall not be included in the PPI proposal to avoid double funding.

The content, tasks and methodologies on pages 11-13 creates a joint project rationale and methodology to develop the PPI proposal.

Possible division of project, phases and content:

First phase

1. **Kick off meeting** planned within 30 days from the signature of the agreement in EASME's premises, followed by an inception report.
2. **Assessment of the public buyers' needs.** This work is covered by the LEA project.
3. **Open market consultation.** This work is covered by the LEA project.

4. **Engaging the market jointly**, This is partly covered by the LEA project and partly by PPI preparations during the first 6 months. Giving to the market signals concerning the size of the procurement in order to trigger the interest of providers (for instance, information regarding the action: when the procurement is expecting to take place, description of the identified needs and what solution is expected to be procured).
5. **Developing the specifications for the call for tenders to be launched**. This is partly covered by the LEA project.

Second phase implementation of the call for tender

1. Publication of the call for tenders for innovative solutions in the Official Journal of the European Union at least in English and on the dedicated project website. Publication on other media is encouraged since it will help increase the visibility of the call for tenders.
2. Evaluation of the received offers on the basis of the award criteria and completion of the award procedure.

Capacity Building and coordination between public buyers including trainings, exchanges, secondment of personnel and other similar practices. Will be done throughout the complete new project.

Progress meeting(s) in EASME's premises, on the spot and/or by remote means of communication to monitor the progress made by the projects. Will be done throughout the project.

Third phase evaluation and dissemination of results

- Purchase, as launch customers, of the innovative solution(s) on offer.
- Co-ordinate the procurement process at least among the participating public procurement bodies. The procurement process must be carried out in full compliance with applicable European and national laws and must take measures to ensure fair competition to independent small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These measures should be outlined in the proposal.
- Evaluation of project as a whole.
- **Communication on the achievements of the projects:** This includes informing the public about the procurement action, about its results and about the level of EU co-financing based upon a communication/dissemination strategy.
- Create and maintain a project website, including updated information, for the duration of the project. The website shall remain accessible for at least two years after the end of the project.

2.5 Guidelines to develop the different stages

Execution stage guidelines

Main activities: **implementation of the PPI and of the PPI contracts** within the timeframe of the project, ensuring deployment of the solutions according to the requirements defined in the preparation stage.

It includes the **deployment of the innovative solutions and evaluation of results of** operating the procured solutions in real-life operating conditions with a duration that allows for appropriate evaluation of the impact of the innovative solutions on the conversion into permanent service.

It includes **dissemination of results, removing obstacles for introducing the PPI** innovations into the market (e.g. contribution to **standardisation**, regulation, certification), awareness raising and experience sharing/training, activities preparing further cooperation among stakeholders and procurers for future PCPs or PPIs.

Tender Documentation and procurement procedure guidelines

- Procurers should avoid the use of selection criteria based on disproportionate qualification and financial guarantee requirements (e.g. with regards to prior customer references and minimum turnover). Functional/performance based specifications must be used, to formulate the object of the PPI tenders as a problem to be solved, without prescribing a specific solution approach to be followed. Evaluation of the tenders must be based on best value for money criteria (not just lowest price).
- The distribution of rights and obligations between procurers and the solution provider(s), including the allocation of IPRs, must be published in the PPI call for tender documents. The PPI calls for tenders must be carried out in a competitive and transparent way in line with the Treaty principles which leads to a price according to market conditions. In order to encourage fair and wide exploitation of results, ownership rights of the Intellectual property (IP) generated during the execution of a PPI contract should be assigned to the party generating the IP, except in duly justified cases (e.g. when that party is not able to exploit them).
- Procurers must organise their procurement so as to avoid any conflict of interest, including in the use of external experts. Potential providers of solutions sought for by a PPI cannot be beneficiaries in an action during which this PPI is planned or undertaken.
- Procurement procedures covered by the EU public procurement directives that do not involve procurement of R&D can be used. Restricted procedures with shortened timeframes for submission of offers for urgency reasons must not be used.

Contract implementation guidelines

- Framework contracts/agreements with lots can be used. For PPIs implemented by a group of procurers, the specific contracts for procuring specific quantities of goods/services for each procurer can be awarded and the selected tenderers can be paid either all by the lead procurer, or by each procurer in the buyers group individually for those quantities of goods/services procured by each procurer individually.

3. National funding PPI

This section contains general information for each LEA consortium partner (covering 9 EU Member States) regarding the application for national co-funding in relation to the H2020 programme and also the possibilities to seek co-funding aligned with the COSME PPI call.

When creating an innovation procurement action plan for participating in an EC co-financed PPI project it is recommended for each of the participating procurers to recognize which of the identified procurement needs in the PPI project that correspond to specific national (local/regional) priorities in order to apply for additional co-funding from national and/or regional funds for their participation.

The resources which are necessary to carry out the PPI action and purchase of the selected solution may, in addition to the co-funding provided by the EU grant, take the form of:

- The beneficiary's own resources (the public organization's own budget for investments in educational technology).
- Funding from its own country's regional EU funds (European Structural and Investment Funds - ESIF).
- Financial contributions from third parties e.g. national and/or regional investment programs.

3.1 Joint or simultaneous use of funds in H2020 programme – co-financing from regional structure funds

In addition to their own procurement budgets, public procurers can obtain co-financing from the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) program to undertake a PPI that match priorities identified in the strategy of their region.

The ESIF are financial instruments approved by the Commission and divided in five different funds which operates under a common framework and fund-specific regulations.

The ESIF programmes are allocated to the EU member states, managed by national authorities and delivered through nationally co-financed multiannual programmes, to develop and support actions related to the Unions key priorities of smart,

sustainable and inclusive growth in line with the objectives of each fund. It is the managing authorities in each member state that makes the ultimate decision of where and how funds are invested at project level within the framework of the relevant programme setting out the specific objectives, results to be achieved and types of action to deliver them. The ESIF programmes support is mainly delivered in the form of grants.

In some of the EU member states two of the funds; the **European Regional Development fund (ERDF)** and the **European Social Fund (ESF)** supports research and innovation as well as education-related projects (thematic objections number 1 and 10 respectively of the ESIF).

Country	Web links to the national authorities managing the ESIF
Austria	www.efre.gv.at ; www.oerok.gv.at/esi-fonds-at/efre/ziel-iwb-efre.html
Belgium	www.vlaio.be/nl/andere-doelgroepen/europees-fonds-voor-regionale-ontwikkeling
Finland	www.rakenerahastot.fi ; www.rakenerahastot.fi/web/en/central-finland
Germany	www.strukturfonds.sachsen.de ; https://europa.sachsen-anhalt.de
Hungary	www.palyazat.gov.hu/rop_ih
Italy	www.miur.gov.it
Portugal	www.ccdr-n.pt
Spain	www.dgfc.sepg.hacienda.gob.es/sitios/DGFC/es-ES/Paginas/inicio.aspx
Sweden	www.tillvaxtverket.se

The Commission services strongly encourage synergies through bringing together the use of Horizon2020 and ESIF in the same project. Public organizations in less developed or transitional EU regions, that wish to participate in the PPI project, may therefore choose to apply for ESIF co-funding instead of H2020 co-funding in order to obtain a higher funding rate for their participation (ESIF 85% respective 60%, H2020 (20%)). (http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/guides/synergy/synergies_en.pdf)

National co-financing constitutes an integral and obligatory part of these programme resources and is covered by a common set of rules applicable to all ESIF and further defined in the fund-specific provisions. The right to combine ESIF and Horizon 2020 does not waive the obligation for the beneficiaries to provide national/regional/own co-funding, if required by the grant agreement.

Example of a PPI project with joint and simultaneous use of funds.

Note that this requires a very strict financial management of the project coordination, where all project partners (beneficiaries) must respect the regulation of both funding sources, and is only possible if funding decisions of the respective programmes are synchronized. As a general rule, it is not allowed to;

- Use any funding (e.g. ESIF, H2020 or other) accumulative to finance the same cost/expenditure items.
- finance the own contribution of the participant (procurement organization) with the funds from e.g. ESIF and/or H2020.

Combined funding of ESIF programmes and Horizon 2020:

- NO substitution of national/regional or private co-funding to EU projects/programmes under direct Commission management by ESIF money (and vice versa).
- NO double financing: in no circumstances shall the same costs be financed twice by any budget.
- Synergies among programmes: Synergies mean joint or coordinated efforts to achieve greater impact and efficiency, not only combining ESIF and Horizon 2020 money in the same project! Synergies can be achieved through:
 - bringing together Horizon 2020 and ESIF money in the same project (that could be a single action or a group of coordinated actions/operations, but always provided that there is no double

funding of the same expenditure item) in view of achieving greater impact and efficiency

- o successive projects that build on each other
- o parallel projects that complement each other.

ESIF programmes could also be designed and implemented to take up high quality project proposals from Horizon 2020 or other centrally managed programmes, for which there is not enough budget available in the respective programmes.

3.2 Joint or simultaneous use of funds in COSME programme – co-financing from regional and/or national funds

In the COSME programme there is no derogation from the non-cumulative principle for funding, meaning that for this program a combination of funds (e.g. ESIF) within the same project is not possible, an action through COSME may only receive one grant from the EU budget.

To ensure this applicants shall indicate the sources and amounts of Union funding received or applied for the same action or part of the action or for its functioning during the same financial year as well as any other funding received or applied for the same action.

In COSME indirect costs are eligible if they are declared on the basis of the flat-rate of 7% of the eligible direct costs.

3.3. Additional/parallel use of national funds

For both H2020 and COSME additional and/or parallel use of own and/or national funds are allowed and encouraged. Presented in the tables below (one for the respective LEA consortium partner's member states), are basic information to simplify the procedure for finding suitable national co-funding to apply for.

Each procurer that will join the upcoming PPI/PCP projects are responsible to take action and make a personal contact to pitch the upcoming PPI/PCP project in their country and apply for additional funding. In the tables below a selection of different organisations/programs are presented.

AUSTRIA	
Organisation/Programme	Austrian Competence Center of Innovation Procurement - IÖB
Web page	www.ioeb.at
Timeline submissions	Will be announced in October 2018 for applications for 2019.
Possible funding rate/budget	(In 2018 ≥ 40 000€) To be announced for 2019.
Specific conditions	To be announced. Application for grants available for PPI in the format of a "Innovation procurement project competition".
Contact persons	Andrea Zens E-mail: andrea.zens@ioeb.at Phone: +43 (1) 245 705 13
Organisation/Programme	Ministry of Education, Science & Research - BMBWF
Web page	www.bmbwf.gv.at
Timeline submissions	To be announced as a new master plan for digitalization in schools is being developed, which plan will replace the current one.
Possible funding rate/budget	To be announced
Specific conditions	Acting as an intermediary and partner for European projects such as Horizon2020 Offering different departments for various subject matters.
Contact persons	To be announced
Organisation/Programme	Austrian Research Promotion Agency - FFG
Web page	www.ffg.at
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/budget	Programme specific
Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	Mag. Andrea Höglinger Direct link: www.ffg.at/team/h-glinger-andrea

BELGIUM (Flanders region)	
Organisation/Programme	Competence center for innovation procurement/PIP – the Programme for Innovation Procurement
Web page	www.innovatieveoverheidsopdrachten.be
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	≥ 50 000€ for validation/test phase prior to procuring an innovative solution.
Specific conditions	Co-funding of PPI for public sector organizations of Flanders region. Nota bene: The Belgian procurement system operates under a legislative framework that splits the authority between federal and regional governments (Wallonia, Brussels (use of specific e-platforms) and Flanders and federal level (publication through the e-Procurement website).
Contacts	www.innovatieveoverheidsopdrachten.be/en/about-pip/pip-team

FINLAND (Central region)	
Organisation/Programme	Business Finland (former TEKES and Finpro)
Web page	www.businessfinland.fi
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	≥ 50 % of eligible project expenses.
Specific conditions	The procurement size must be large enough to boost the sector, at least on a regional scale. The planning and preparation of innovative public procurements must include cooperation with potential providers and end-users.
Contact persons	Ms. Piia Moilanen +358(0) 2950 55 748 piia.moilanen@businessfinland.fi

GERMANY (RSA)	
Organisation/Programme	Federal Funding Advisory Service
Web page	https://www.foerderinfo.bund.de/index.php
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	Programme specific

Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	+0800 26 23 008 beratung@foerderinfo.bund.de
Organisation/Programme	Federal Ministry of Education and Research - BMBF
Web page	www.bmbf.de
Timeline submissions	Programme specific
Possible funding rate/ budget	Programme specific
Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	+ 030/18 57 0 bmbf@bmbf.bund.de

HUNGARY

Organisation/Programme	National Research, Development and Innovation Office - NKFI
Web page	http://nkfih.gov.hu/
Timeline submissions	Programme specific http://nkfih.gov.hu/english-2017/funding-schemes/open-calls
Possible funding rate/ budget	Programme specific
Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	Department of Fund Management and Innovation Pál Péter Szalai (+36 1) 795 4855 pal.peter.szalai@nkfih.gov.hu

ITALY

Organisation/Programme	Ministry of Education, University and Research – MIUR/PON Scuola
Web page	http://www.miur.gov.it/
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	N/A
Specific conditions	In the National Operation Programme for School 2014-2020 (PON Scuola) support for PCP/PPI actions are explicitly mentioned (Action 11.3.1). To date no available funds of PCP/PPI actions from MIUR but support for capacity building.

Contact persons	http://www.istruzione.it/pon/ http://www.istruzione.it/pon/asse05_finanziamenti.html
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PORTUGAL	
Organisation/Programme	Instituição Financeira de Desenvolvimento - IFD
Web page	www.ifd.pt/pt/
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	Programme specific
Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	+351 222 452 020 ifdgeral@ifd.pt
Organisation/Programme	Portugal 2020
Web page	www.portugal2020.pt
Timeline submissions	Programme specific
Possible funding rate/ budget	Programme specific
Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	https://www.portugal2020.pt/Portal2020/programas-operacionais-portugal-2020-2

SPAIN (Catalonia region)	
Organisation/Programme	FCRI - Fundació Institució Catalana de Suport a la Reserca
Web page	http://www.fundaciorecerca.cat
Timeline submissions	Programme specific
Possible funding rate/ budget	Programme specific
Specific conditions	Programme specific
Contact persons	+34 93 268 77 00 info@fundaciorecerca.cat

SWEDEN (West of Sweden)	
Organisation/Programme	Sweden's Innovation Agency - Vinnova
Web page	www.vinnova.se
Timeline submissions	www.vinnova.se/sok-finansiering/hitta-finansiering/
Possible funding rate/ budget	Depending on the specific call.
Specific conditions	Funding available through announced calls.
Contact persons	Mr. Johan Lindberg +46 8 454 64 53 johan.lindberg@vinnova.se
Organisation/Programme	Region Halland
Web page	www.regionhalland.se
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	Depending on the specific call.
Specific conditions	Application for funding available through submission of project description according to pre-set application form
Contact persons	Ms. Ulrika Bertilsson + 46 35 17 98 27 Ulrika.Bertilsson@regionhalland.se
Organisation/Programme	Västra Götalands regionen
Web page	https://www.vgregion.se/regional-utveckling/soka-stod/
Timeline submissions	N/A
Possible funding rate/ budget	Depending on the specific call.
Specific conditions	Application for funding available through submission of project description according to pre-set application form
Contact persons	www.vgregion.se/regional-utveckling/kontakt/

4. EU funding ICT-34: Open to ICT based solutions in any area of public interest (€ 6M; 28 March 2019)

This section contains details on a possible PCP call for LEA procurers. It covers the call text, analysis of the call and a possible PCP project rationale.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/ict-34-2018-2019.html>

4.1 Call extract

Specific Challenge:

The challenge is to **enable public procurers to collectively implement PCPs** in order to close the gap between supply and demand for innovative ICTs. The objective is to bring radical improvements to the quality and efficiency of public services by encouraging the development and validation of breakthrough solutions through PCP.

Scope:

PCP actions targeting consortia of procurers with **similar procurement needs** that want to procure together the development of innovative ICT based solutions to **modernize public services** whilst creating growth opportunities for industry and researchers in Europe in new markets. This topic is open to proposals for PCP actions in all areas of public sector interest requiring innovative ICT based solutions. It is open both to proposals requiring improvements mainly based on one specific ICT technology field, as well as to proposals requiring end-to-end solutions that need combinations of different ICT technologies.

Proposals shall demonstrate sustainability of the action beyond the life of the project. Activities covered **shall include cooperation with policy makers to reinforce the national policy frameworks and mobilise substantial additional national budgets for PCP and PPI**, as well as **awareness raising, technical assistance and/or capacity building** to other procurers beyond the project to **mainstream PCP/PPI implementation** and to remove obstacles for introducing the innovative solutions to be procured into the market.

The Commission considers a contribution from the EU of up to 6 million €.

Expected Impact:

- Reduced fragmentation of demand for innovative solutions;
- Increased opportunities for wide market uptake and economies of scale for the supply side through the use of joint specifications, wide publication of results and where relevant contribution to standardisation, regulation or certification.

Funding rate:

The eligible costs of **coordination and networking activities may not exceed 30%** of the total estimated eligible costs set up in the budget of the action at the signature of the grant agreement. Indirect eligible costs are calculated as a flat rate of 25% of direct eligible costs, excluding direct eligible costs for subcontracting (e.g the price of the PCP procurement) and costs of resources made available by third parties which are not used on the premises of the beneficiary (e.g test equipment)

4.2 Analysis of the call

- Minimum 2 procurers from 2 different countries adding support partners.
- Open for Digital Education.
- 6 million € of funding in total.
- CSA budget 1.8 million €.
- CP budget 4.2 million € (90% of the complete R&D purchase funded by EC) and 10 % funded by procurers).

4.3 PCP project rationale

The following content and steps are to be used to develop the proposal and the workplan of the upcoming PCP project:

Preparations and PCP methodology:

- Common identified need and user cases
- Open market consultation
- Preparing ITT documentation
- Capacity building seminars for procurers

Launch the PCP call:

- PCP stages 1-3
- Preparation of evaluation and testing boards and panels
- Awareness rising campaigns
- Strategic work to involve policy level

Final evaluation and standards:

- Mainstream model of PCP

3. Final words and recommendations

Compulsary decisions and steps to follow within LEA

Before proceeding with the PPI call (Submission of proposal in December 2018) some necessary steps for LEA procurers are to:

- Commit to LEA PPI preparations based up the signed GA (deadline November 2018 at the LEA Consortium meeting in Braga, Portugal).
- Agree upon a common demand/needs (deadline November 2018 at the LEA Consortium meeting in Braga, Portugal). Each procurer explores and contacts national authorities for public funding to combine with the PPI funding from EC.
- Take decision on joint cross border PPI and any national differences on demand and challenges to be tackled by suppliers.
- Commit minimum 3 procurers to the upcoming PPI call by December 2018. In order to fulfill the signed GA, procurers that do not commit to participate in the upcoming LEA PPI are advised to find and present a replacement procurer.

Recommendations on how to proceed beyond LEA

As first movers within PCP/PPI LEA procurers need to minimize risks and apply for joint-funding to cover workload, part of the purchase investments of the innovations and to spread the lessons learned to other stakeholders in Europe.

In order to reach LEA objectives and to create a sustainable future of the ongoing work of innovation procurement in Education and to reach beyond LEA our recommendations are:

- Gather 3-5 LEA procurers to commit for the PPI call in December 2018 as presented in this report.
- The same LEA procurers parallel work to identify national funding according to the channels identified in this report.

- Gather 3 -5 procurers (in and outside LEA using Followers and LEA-N) to commit for the PCP call in March 2019 presented in this report.

Timeline to develop the proposal

